

On the limitations of Machine Learning (ML) methodologies in predicting the wake characteristics of wind turbines

Ng Yin Kwee

School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering,
College of Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore
MYKNG@ntu.edu.sg

Abstract

Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have been more prevalent in recent years, and they are being used to tackle complicated issues across a broad range of fields. Wind energy is not an exception, as ML has recently been applied to wind turbine blade design, wake velocity and wake turbulence intensity prediction, and even wind farm optimization. The immense learning ability of ML models enables them to be trained to predict and regress a complex relationship with a high degree of accuracy. However, data for testing ML models often originate from the same rotor simulation used for training, with just slight variations in operating conditions. This research aims to investigate the generalizability of ML-based wake prediction models, i.e., whether ML can correctly predict wake properties using data from a different wind turbine that was not taken for training. This investigation's observation shows that a generalized ML wake model requires training data from multiple turbines with a wide range of operating conditions. In addition, advanced regularization, complex loss functions, and ML methods that focus on capturing the physics (such as Physics Informed Artificial Neural Networks (PINN) and symbolic regression) can be utilized.

Keywords: Wake velocity, turbulence intensity, Support Vector Regression (SVR), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost).

Short biography

Prof. Eddie is elected as:

Academician for European Academy of Sciences and Arts (EASA, EU);
Fellow of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (FASME, USA);
Fellow of Institute of Engineering and Technology (FIET, United Kingdom);
Fellow of International Engineering and Technology Institute (FIETI, Hong Kong),
Distinguished Fellow for Institute of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence, (DFIDSAI, China), and, Academician for Academy of Pedagogy and Learning, (USA).
He has published numerous papers in SCI-IF int. journal (430); int. conf. proceedings (130), textbook chapters (>105) and others (32) over the 29 years. Co-edited 14 books in STEM areas.
He is the:
Lead Editor-in-Chief for the ISI Journal of Mechanics in Medicine and Biology for dissemination of original research in all fields of mechanics in medicine and biology since 2000;
Founding Editor-in-Chief for the ISI indexed Journal of Medical Imaging and Health Informatics;
Associate editor or EAB of various referred international journals such as Applied Intelligence, BioMedical Engineering OnLine, Computers in Biology & Medicine, and, Journal of Advanced Thermal Science Research..

IEECP'22, July 21-22, 2022, Oxford, United Kingdom

Copyright: © 2022 by the author(s) | Licensee IEECP – SCI-INDEX

Open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of CC BY license.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

